

Book of abstracts

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Title: The Book of Abstracts of the 2nd International Meeting on Deep Eutectic Systems

Publishes abstracts from the following fields: Fundamentals, Pharma, Food, Extraction & Separation, Materials and Biotech.

Publishers: Des Solutio - Soluções e Consultoria Científica, Lda

ISBN: 978-989-33-1955-0

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Stabilisation of Aromas: Supercritical Carbon Dioxide Extraction Coupled with Deep Eutectic Solvents

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Keywords: aroma, supercritical carbon dioxide, deep eutectic solvent

Due to their numerous pharmacological and sensory properties, the significance of natural aromas has long been recognised. Moreover, their application in different industries is constantly increasing including the pharmaceutical, cosmetics, beverage, and food industry. Conventional methods of isolation of these mixtures of volatile compounds are time-consuming and non-selective. Therefore, these shortcomings have been overcome with the development of superior extraction approaches. Supercritical carbon dioxide extraction (ScCO₂) is an established green and highly efficient technology for isolation of aromas present in different natural matrices. Despite the efficiency of this process, the instability of aromas limits their application. For these reasons and in addition to defining optimal extraction procedures for the recovery of aromas, it is necessary to define an optimal procedure that will provide the stability of aromatic volatile compounds and secure their properties in the long term. Deep eutectic solvents (DES) are solvents of high absorption capacity in which various natural compounds have high solubility. Additionally, these alternative solvents are affordable, biodegradable, and easy for manipulation.

Therefore, the main goal of this study is to develop and optimize a procedure for isolation and stabilisation of aromas. The extraction of aromas from different natural materials will be performed using ScCO₂. By varying process parameters and analyzing their impact on the extraction efficacy and chemical composition of the extracts, the most optimal extraction parameters will be established. The following step will be to stabilise aromas with DES by dispersing the recovered aromas in DES. To achieve optimal stabilisation, characterization and optimization of DES systems will be conducted. In addition, the chemical profile of stabilised aromas will be monitored during storage under different conditions.

Acknowledgements: *This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101003396.*